

Acetylation of the amino group in β -lactams under aqueous conditions: Effects of ring sizes

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Monocyclic *cis* and *trans* amino β -lactams are acetylated with 2-bromo-2-phenylacetyl chloride in aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution. The same reaction with 6-aminopenicillanic acid follows a different pathway and produces an oxazolone.

Keywords: Amino β -lactam, acetylation, rearrangement, ring size.

Introduction

Azitiidin-2-ones are very important chemotherapeutic molecules owing to their wide-range of pharmacological activities¹⁻⁴. The chemistry and biology of β -lactams antibiotics and related compounds are extensively investigated⁵⁻⁸. Since the discovery of penicillin by Alexander Fleming in 1928, new era of modern medicine has started⁹. The most important classes of β -lactam antibiotics viz. penicillin and cephalosporin have β -lactams ring fused either to five or six membered heterocyclic moiety. These molecular structures have opened numerous research possibilities on the design and synthesis of diverse class of β -lactam antibiotics. In 1976, the isolation of nocardicins, a monocyclic β -lactam from broth of bacterial species *Nocardia uniformis*¹⁰ followed by the seminal research of isolation of other notable monobactam, *sulfazecin* and *isosulfazecin* from strain of *Pseudomonas* is reported¹¹. This pioneer research suggest that the classically fused β -lactam rings might not be crucial for their chemotherapeutic activity in enzyme inhibitory progression^{6,12,13}. The first synthetic monobactam viz. aztreonam for a clinical application further supported monobactam as the leading compounds in drug discovery¹⁴.

Herein we wish to report acetylation of *cis* and *trans* amino β -lactams in aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution and further extended to this strategy to 6-aminopenicillanic towards the synthesis of important heterocyclic compound, oxazolone through a ring rupture-rearrangement reaction. This study suggests that the stability of monocyclic β -lactams is superior to bicyclic β -lactams in aqueous alkali solution.

Results and discussion

3-Amino-azitiidin-2-ones are the central motif in penicillin and the key functional groups responsible for the inhibition of penicillin-binding protein (PBPs) in bacterial cell wall. Therefore, the synthesis of amino β -lactams is the subject of intense study since 1970. There are several reports on the synthesis and biological activities of these types of compounds¹⁵. In our earlier studies, synthesis of *cis* and *trans* amino β -lactams was reported¹⁶⁻²¹. Amide formation is one of the most common reactions to convert an amino group to suitable derivatives and therapeutically relevant peptides.

Freidinger in 1980 designed β -lactam dipeptides in β -turn mimetics and peptidomimetics based on functionalization of amino group in β -lactam scaffolds²²⁻²⁵. In 2-azetidiones,

functionalization of amino group to amides is done by many researchers because most of the antibiotics have amide chains^{26,27}. Moreover, suitable amide-containing β -lactams are useful substrates for other reactions including rearrangement through nucleophilic process.

The N-acylation and formylation of amine are important reaction in synthetic organic chemistry because it frequently encountered in diverse bioactive molecules^{28,29}.

Herein we report a highly efficient green protocol of N-acylation of 3-amino-azetidine-2-ones using 10% aq. solution of sodium carbonate (Scheme 1). This protocol shows wide range of substrate compatibility with excellent yield at room temperature.

In our preliminary investigation, we have taken β -lactam, (3R,4S)-3-amino-1-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4-phenylazetidin-2-

one (**1a**) as the reference to conduct the reaction and was treated with 2-bromo-2-phenylacetyl chloride (**2**) (1 equiv.) in presence of 0.2 mL of 10% aq. Na_2CO_3 in THF and yield of 80% of **3a** was obtained (Table 1, entry 1). It was worthy to note that there was no hydrolysis of the β -lactam ring during our investigation. This exciting result prompted us to perform the N-acylation reaction with diverse β -lactam amines **1b-c** under identical reaction conditions. In all instances very clean reaction with excellent yield of the products was obtained (Scheme 1, Table 1).

In a similar manner we also carried out N-acylation reaction of *trans*-3-amino-azetidin-2-ones with excellent yield (Scheme 2, Table 2). Despite the basic reaction conditions there was no decomposition of the *cis* and *trans* β -lactam rings.

Scheme 1. N-Acylation of 3-aminoazetidinone with 2-bromo-2-phenylacetylchloride under aq. condition with 10% Na_2CO_3 solution.

Table 1. N-Acylation of *cis*-3-aminoazetidinone with 10% aq. Na_2CO_3 (0.2–0.3 mL) solution at 0–25°C

Entry	Ar ¹	Ar ²	3	Temp. (°C)	Base (10 mol%) (mL)	Yield ^a (%)
1	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	3a	0–25	0.2	80
2	C ₆ H ₅	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	3b	0–25	0.3	90
3	C ₆ H ₅	4-FC ₆ H ₄	3c	0–25	0.2	85
4	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	3d	0–25	0.3	80
5	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	3e	0–25	0.3	85

^aIsolated yield.

Scheme 2. N-Acylation of *trans*-3-aminoazetidinone with 2-bromo-2-phenylacetylchloride under aq. condition with 10% Na_2CO_3 solution.

Table 2. N-Acylation of *trans*-3-amino-azitidi-2-one with 10% aq. Na₂CO₃ (0.2–0.3 mL) solution at 0–25°C

Entry	Ar ¹	Ar ²	5 [a-c]	Temp. (°C)	Base (10 mol%) (mL)	Yield ^a (%)
1	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	5a	0–25	0.2	80
2	C ₆ H ₅	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	5b	0–25	0.3	80
3	C ₆ H ₅	4-FC ₆ H ₄	5c	0–25	0.2	85
4	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	5d	0–25	0.3	80
5	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	5e	0–25	0.3	85

^aisolated yield.**Scheme 3.** Base induced N-acylation followed by rearrangement to oxazolidine derivatives (**7**).

It was interesting to note that under stronger basic condition viz. aq. NaOH/KOH, significant hydrolysis of β -lactam ring was observed. Therefore, N-acylation was performed under mild basic condition to avoid the possibility of hydrolysis.

Under our standardized protocol there was also no epimerization at C-3 and C-4 centers in lactam ring.

The 3-amino- β -lactam **1a-e** and **2a-e** was easily accessible by [2+2] cycloaddition reaction ketene derived from N-phthalimidoglycyl chloride or acid with imine via Staudinger [2+2] cycloaddition strategy from our earlier reported methods^{30,31}.

A similar treatment of **6** under identical conditions underwent rearrangement of the β -lactam ring. The initially formed intermediate **6a** attacked the β -lactam carbonyl group and cleaved the ring in the presence of base to form **6b**. The

intermediate **6b** on elimination of hydrobromic acid afforded the conjugated product **7**. Clearly, bicyclic β -lactam **6** was capable of undergoing these series of structural alterations due to severe strain present in it. The strain present in monocyclic β -lactams **1** and **2** were not enough for this rearrangement reaction (Scheme 3).

Conclusions

A few *cis* and *trans* β -lactam amides were prepared from the corresponding amino β -lactams by simple treatment of an acid chloride with a mild base in aqueous solution. The same reaction with 6-aminopenicillanic acid followed an entirely different route and produced an oxazolone. The differences in the reactivities of these amines **3** and **5** were because of strain associated with the β -lactam ring in **5**. Oxazolone reported herein is highly functionalized within a small frame-structure. Moreover products **3** and **5** are also

suitable to study rearrangement of β -lactams under relatively more drastic conditions. It is therefore, obvious that simple reactions in water with sodium carbonate can really afford important products that are highly useful in chemical research.

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